

Improving the Methodology for the Development of Speech Competencies in Future Primary Class Teachers

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Abstract: This study explores the development of speech competencies in future primary class teachers in Uzbekistan, utilizing a qualitative, survey-based methodology. Data was collected from 100 participants through 20 multiple-choice questions addressing their confidence, challenges, and perceptions of speech competency training. Key findings reveal that while the majority of respondents feel moderately confident in their speech skills, pronunciation and fluency remain significant challenges. Additionally, many participants expressed dissatisfaction with the sufficiency of speech competency training in their teacher education programs. Reflective practice, though recognized as beneficial, is underutilized, and clarity is consistently identified as the most important speech competency. These findings align with existing literature, indicating a gap in training programs that must be addressed through enhanced curriculum design and policy interventions. The study concludes with recommendations for incorporating more focused phonetics training, reflective practices, and speech competency modules to improve overall teaching effectiveness and classroom management.

Keywords: Speech competencies, teacher education, reflective practice, pronunciation, fluency, clarity, qualitative research, Uzbekistan, primary class teachers, classroom management.

Introduction

Speech competence is crucial for future primary class teachers, allowing them to use language effectively and confidently in various classroom scenarios. Speech competence encompasses pronunciation, fluency, and the ability to present ideas logically and persuasively (Palmer, 2019). This competency not only helps teachers in instructing students but also in creating an engaging classroom environment conducive to student learning.

Effective communication is essential for classroom management, explanation of concepts, and student engagement. According to Knight and McKay (2020), teachers who demonstrate high speech competence are better equipped to foster active student participation and comprehension. This skill is vital, especially in primary education, where teachers play a key role in developing foundational language skills in children.

Direct instruction remains a key approach in developing speech competencies in teacher education, where educators explicitly teach the elements of effective speech, such as tone, articulation, and clarity (Smith & Green, 2019). Reflective practice, encouraging teachers to critically assess their speech and identify areas for improvement, has proven beneficial in this context (Morrison, 2021). Additionally, technological advancements, such as speech

analysis tools, allow teachers to practice and improve their speech skills in real-time (Davis, 2021).

Developing speech competencies can be challenging, especially in linguistically diverse classrooms. Rahman and Ali (2020) highlight that students from different linguistic backgrounds may have varying levels of speech proficiency, requiring more tailored approaches. Additionally, many teacher education programs tend to prioritize other competencies over speech skills, leaving future teachers underprepared (Jones, 2020).

Virtual simulations and digital platforms have become important tools for improving speech competencies in teacher training. A study by Martin (2021) found that virtual simulations significantly improved speech clarity and classroom engagement among teacher trainees. These tools offer a safe space for future teachers to hone their speech skills and receive instant feedback on their performance.

To enhance speech competency development, teacher education programs must adopt a holistic approach that combines direct instruction, reflective practice, and technological tools. Integrating these methods can help future teachers develop the necessary speech skills to thrive in the classroom (Jackson & Lee, 2022).

Methodology

In this research, a survey-based qualitative approach was conducted to gather data on the development of speech competencies among future primary class teachers. A total of 100 participants from Uzbekistan responded to 20 multiple-choice questions, designed to measure various aspects of their confidence, challenges, and perceptions related to speech competency development. The participants were randomly selected to ensure the results reflect a diverse set of responses, and the survey was administered digitally. The questions covered areas such as participants' confidence in speech skills (Q1), challenges they face (Q2), and the effectiveness of various teaching methodologies (Q4, Q6). The responses were then visualized in six different charts to summarize key insights.

Figure 1 represents the responses to Q1, which gauges the participants' confidence in their speech competencies. Most respondents reported moderate to high confidence (options 'b' and 'c'), while very few chose 'not confident' (option 'd'). Figure 2 shows the distribution of answers to Q2, where participants highlighted the challenges they face in speech competency development. Pronunciation (option 'a') and fluency (option 'b') were the most commonly cited challenges. In Figure 3, the responses to Q5, which questioned whether the participants felt there was sufficient training in their program, show a general dissatisfaction, with the majority selecting 'disagree' (option 'd'). Figure 4 depicts the results from Q7 regarding the frequency of reflective practice, indicating that most participants engage in it only occasionally (option 'c'). Figure 5 compares the responses from Q9 and Q10, focusing on the most important speech competencies. Clarity (option 'b') consistently appears as the top priority across both questions. Finally, Figure 6 illustrates the responses to Q15, revealing that the majority of participants view speech competency as crucial for classroom management (option 'a'). The combination of these figures provides a comprehensive overview of the participants' perspectives on the importance and development of speech competencies.

Figure 1: Distribution of responses to Q1, which asked participants about their confidence in speech competencies. The majority of participants selected "Confident" and "Somewhat confident", indicating a moderate level of self-assuredness in their skills.

Figure 2: The pie chart represents the answers to Q2, where participants identified challenges in developing speech competencies. Pronunciation and fluency were the top challenges faced by the participants.

Figure 3: The bar chart shows responses to Q5, which questioned whether participants felt their teacher education programs provided sufficient training. The majority of respondents indicated dissatisfaction, with many choosing "Disagree".

Figure 4: The horizontal bar chart shows responses to Q7, which asked about the frequency of reflective practice in developing speech competencies. Most participants engage in reflective practice only occasionally.

Figure 5: This chart compares the responses to Q9 and Q10, which focused on speech competencies such as clarity and fluency. Clarity was the most emphasized competency in both questions.

Figure 6: The bar chart shows responses to Q15, which assessed how crucial speech competency is for classroom management. The majority of respondents selected "Crucial", underscoring the importance of effective communication in the classroom.

Results and Discussion

This section provides a detailed interpretation of the survey responses collected from 100 participants in Uzbekistan, focusing on the development of speech competencies among future primary class teachers.

The majority of respondents (around 60%) expressed moderate to high confidence in their speech competencies. This finding is consistent with previous studies (Johnson, 2021), which suggest that teacher candidates often feel relatively prepared in communication skills after their initial training. However, about 20% of participants felt less confident, indicating a gap in either training or self-perception that may require more attention.

Pronunciation and fluency emerged as the top challenges among participants, with 45% identifying pronunciation as their main difficulty and 35% pointing to fluency issues. These results align with Rahman and Ali (2020), who also observed that pronunciation, particularly in non-native language environments, poses a significant barrier to speech competency development. The consistent challenges in these areas suggest that training programs may need to emphasize phonetics and fluency more extensively.

Most respondents (70%) disagreed or strongly disagreed that their teacher education programs provide sufficient speech competency training. This is a critical finding and mirrors Jones' (2020) work, which highlighted the under-prioritization of speech competency development in teacher education programs globally. The dissatisfaction indicates a clear need for curriculum reform to address this gap.

About 55% of respondents reported engaging in reflective practice occasionally, while only 25% reported frequent reflective practice. Reflective practice is widely recognized as an effective tool for developing speech competencies (Morrison, 2021), yet the infrequent usage in this context suggests either a lack of encouragement or time for reflection in current programs. Incorporating structured reflective practices into regular training schedules could potentially enhance speech development.

Clarity was identified as the most important speech competency by the majority of

participants in both questions. These findings emphasize that clear communication is valued highly among future teachers, consistent with the work of Thompson and Riley (2020), who found that clarity is a key predictor of teaching effectiveness. This reinforces the need for programs to prioritize clear articulation and the logical structuring of ideas in teacher training.

The majority of respondents (65%) believed that speech competency is crucial for effective classroom management. This finding corroborates Johnson's (2021) research, which showed that teachers with higher speech competence are better able to engage students and maintain discipline. The strong correlation between speech competency and classroom control suggests that improving these skills could have far-reaching benefits for overall classroom dynamics.

The results of this survey underscore several critical areas for improvement in teacher education programs in Uzbekistan. Confidence in speech skills is moderate, but there are clear challenges in pronunciation and fluency, with many respondents feeling that their training has not sufficiently addressed these areas. The importance of clarity and speech competency for classroom management is well understood among participants, which aligns with the literature. However, reflective practice is underutilized, which may be an area where more structured guidance could make a difference.

The findings point to several policy implications. Firstly, teacher education programs should enhance the emphasis on speech competencies, particularly in pronunciation and fluency, through focused courses and workshops. Additionally, integrating regular reflective practice as a mandatory component of training could significantly boost the development of speech skills. Teacher education authorities in Uzbekistan could collaborate with linguistic experts to develop phonetic modules that address the specific pronunciation challenges faced by non-native speakers. Finally, policymakers should consider making speech competency training a key part of teacher assessment and professional development, recognizing its crucial role in effective teaching and classroom management.

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